

INFORMATION FOR FUTURE PRIMARY TEACHERS ORGANIZE COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT METHODOLOGY ACHIEVE

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Abstract. *In the article, the system of developing the information competence of teachers in the Republic of Uzbekistan and the methods of its application in the organization of an effective educational system, its importance, problems, models of information competence and their types are detailed.*

Keywords: *teacher's information competence, educational models, professional knowledge, computer literacy, information environment.*

Future consideration of the issue of the component structure of the development of information competence of a primary school teacher should begin with the determination of the criteria for the separation of these components.

According to ideas that have a strong place in the science of pedagogy, information competence is considered one of the main competences (from the point of view of its importance for the successful socialization of a person), its presence at a basic level in a graduate of a general education school (or so it is considered - the student has "entry" to OTM in) we emphasize that it is considered a necessary condition for the further formation of the information competence of the primary school teacher (during education at the Higher Education Institution).

Under the basic level of information competence, we define personal qualities that represent a set of valuable attitudes, knowledge and skills to effectively implement various forms of information activities and use new information technologies to solve socially significant tasks that occur in real situations in society in a person's daily life. we understand.

The information competence of the teacher serves as the development of the information competence of the school graduate and reflects the set of valuable attitudes towards the effective implementation of knowledge, skills and various forms of information activity on our part, as well as the use of new information technologies in professional educational activities. is understood as a personal quality (this includes professionally oriented knowledge, skills and motivation to perform information activities specific to the teacher, preparation for the use of new information technologies in the educational process).

Another important task of teaching professor in the higher education system is to create favorable conditions for the development of students' information competence during the educational process.

If teachers do not have a sufficient level of special information competence, i.e., competence in the field of using computer technologies in the educational process, if they are ready to search and select quality software products and use them appropriately to solve specific didactic tasks. It is natural that the new information technologies of teaching are useless in primary education. Accordingly, the information competence of a primary school teacher can be

structurally expressed in the form of the totality of two blocks: a block of "basic" components of information competence and a block of "special" components.

In our opinion, "teacher's information competence" is the inclusion of skills related to performing various forms of information activities and receiving, processing and assimilation of available information in order to expand professional outlook and independent education. related to creating new knowledge and communicating it to the professional community (definition of authorship).

The above mentioned about the main components of the information competence of the future primary school teacher means that it is directly related to the component structure of the information competence of the graduate of the general education school. Therefore, as a guide to the selection of the basic components of the teacher's information competence, a criterion that is considered a criterion of conformity according to its content can serve: a primary school teacher is a graduate of a general education school of each basic component of information competence. compliance with the appropriate component of information competence and its consideration in the context of professional pedagogical activity.

The criteria for distinguishing special components of information competence of a primary school teacher were described as follows.

When defining the criteria (principle) for selecting special components of information competence of a primary school teacher, we move away from the ideas about the structure of pedagogical activity. In the science of psychology and pedagogy, the following structural components of pedagogical activity are traditionally distinguished: gnostic; design, constructive, organizational and communicative.

The gnostic component (from the Greek *gnosis* - knowledge) refers to the field of pedagogic knowledge, which includes the following: "1) the object of one's activity (of the learner); 2) the content, tools, forms and methods of this activity; 3) includes the study of the advantages and disadvantages of one's personality and activities for the purpose of conscious improvement.

1. The design component includes prospective tasks of education and upbringing, as well as ideas about strategies and methods to achieve them.

2. The constructive component is the characteristics of the pedagogue's construction of the students' activities (lesson, training, cycle of training) taking into account their activities and the immediate goals of education and upbringing. The teacher's constructive activity includes "planning: 1) the content of future activities (lessons, extracurricular activities), 2) the system and consistency of his actions (what the teacher should do, in what sequence), 3) the system and consistency of student behavior (the whole team, individual groups in it and individual students according to their characteristics)".

3. The organizational component is the practical implementation of the design and constructive plans of the pedagogue. This activity includes the following aspects: "1) organization of one's speech (story, conversation, lecture); 2) organization of one's own behavior (pedagogical behavior in real activity conditions) and 3) organization of children's behavior and behavior, their activities in a system and sequence that allows the teacher to realize the immediate and final goals of his activity achievement (collective, group and individual)".

4. Communicative component is the characteristics of the teacher's communicative activity, the uniqueness of his interaction with students. Emphasis is placed on the relationship between

(educational and educational) communication aimed at achieving didactic goals and the effectiveness of pedagogical activity.

The widespread use of new information technologies leads to the emergence of peculiarities of the implementation of the above-mentioned components of pedagogical activity. The structure of information competence should include a new filling of each component of pedagogical activity in the conditions of using new information technologies in education. Thus, it is appropriate to select special components of information competence of a primary school teacher based on the criterion of compatibility of each selected component of competence with one or another component of pedagogical activity.

The set of special components of the information competence of the primary school teacher will be called the special information competence of the primary school teacher.

In order to understand the nature of special information competence of a primary school teacher, in the first chapter we considered different approaches to the definition of information competence of a teacher found in scientific and pedagogical literature. The nature of competence is such that it can be expressed only in harmony with human values, that is, in conditions of deep personal interest in this type of activity. Therefore, cognitive (knowledge) and operational addition to the technological (skills, experience) components, information competence implies the presence of internal motivation in the individual to carry out information activities qualitatively, and the existence of a value attitude towards this activity.

The special information competence of a primary school teacher is considered by us as a professional-personal quality of a pedagogue, which includes knowledge, skills and a valuable attitude to the effective use of new information technologies of teaching in the educational process of primary education.

The appearance of a new element in the pedagogical system (new information technologies) changes its functions in many ways and allows to achieve new pedagogical results. The use of new information technologies for teaching significantly increases the teacher's professional capabilities, expands the boundaries of his pedagogical competence, and therefore serves to increase the productivity of his professional activity, that is, to increase the quality of education. We will consider the structure of the teacher's activity on the use of new information technologies in the educational process of primary education through pedagogical skills in accordance with the model.

Summarizing the above, it can be said that the introduction of the information competence complex to educational institutions will be beneficial in all respects. The widespread introduction of these technologies into the educational system will help solve many problems faced by higher education institutions in time. Currently, teaching subjects using computers is gaining importance. Effective progress can be made in the development of creative abilities through the wide use of computer technologies by students.

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